

Topological Characteristics and Entropy Measures of Armchair Hexagonal Cycloarene Structures

Süleyman Ediz^{*1}

¹Department of Mathematics and Science Education, Van Yüzüncü Yıl University, Türkiye.

Abstract

Topological indices, which were identified by applying graph-theoretical techniques, are precise chemical descriptors that are very helpful in relating molecules to their physical properties. Making cycloarenes, a subclass of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons, requires the circular arrangement of benzene rings. Due to their peculiar electrical properties and pore structure, which enable their quick practical application, these molecules have recently attracted a lot of attention. In this paper, we formulate analytically the various R, S, and Van indices of the armchair hexagonal cycloarene structure. We also provide a topological index-based Shannon's entropy computation by using the R, S, and Van topological indices concepts.

Keywords: Cycloarene; Shannon's entropy; Topological descriptors; Van index; S index; R index

1. Introduction

The concept of chemical graph theory is applied in the topology branch of mathematical chemistry. It became more well-known as a result of the applications of graph theory for the mathematical modeling of chemical properties that its proponents demonstrated [1]. Chemists have determined through a significant body of experimental data that a compound's molecular structure and physicochemical characteristics are strongly connected. Later, more sophisticated graph-theoretical methods were created to characterize various chemical compound features. The idea of topological indices, which are specific network invariants, is one such crucial tool. Due to their usage in creating quantitative structure-activity (QSAR) and quantitative structure-property relationships (QSPR), which connect a substance's chemical structure to its properties [2, 3], they are becoming more and more important.

The introduction of novel entropy measures based on R, S, and Van topological indices as well as the calculation of defined entropies of the armchair hexagonal cycloarene (AHC(n,p)) structure are the main goals of this study. This makes it simpler to discover complex substances' various physicochemical properties, which might be difficult to

ascertain using experimental procedures. Because they maximize efficacy and cost, they are frequently utilized in the area of computer-aided pharmaceutical development. The mathematical invention and evolution of indices that provide precise links between structures and their functions have been the subject of various studies over time [4–6]. A chemical structure known as a benzenoid hydrocarbon system lacks non-hexagonal inner faces due to the fusion of hexagonal carbon rings [7]. Instead, a benzenoid system's outer face is bounded by hexagons, and after producing a coronoid hydrocarbon system, a finite number of hexagonal rings are eliminated from the system's interior [8]. Browse [9, 10] and the references therein for more information on coronoid systems and their subclasses. When cycloarenes like kekulene, which are made through linear and angular annulations of benzene units, were discovered, research on benzenoid and coronoid hydrocarbons began [11]. Topological index-based Shannon's entropy calculation using a self-powered multiplicative index concept is a viable replacement for the traditional thermodynamic entropy notion [12]. Due to the vast range of uses of coronoid structures, theoretical and experimental research on them later became extensive. Huge polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAH) are good

¹ Received: 15 September 2023

*Corresponding author.

E-mail address: suleymanediz@yyu.edu.tr (S. Ediz)

examples of model molecules for graphite sheets as well as other carbon-based materials [13]. Their function in transporting metal ions by accommodating them is explained by their electrical properties caused by their super aromaticity and appropriate pore diameters. The majority of these PAHs are remnants of specific mineral oil-related chemical reactions, some of which are very harmful to the environment. This calls for the investigation of their characteristics using both theoretical and experimental techniques [10]. Cycloarenes are recently discovered macrocycles composed of several benzene rings joined together in a linear and angular pattern. The first cycloarene, kekulene, was synthesized in 1978, which led to a lot of inquiries and additional research into the conjugation of macrocycles. Similar cycloarene septulene [14] strengthened several facts regarding the electrical along magnetic properties of this specific PAH class. Currently, numerous studies are being conducted to understand these compounds' super aromaticity, which explains their increased thermodynamic stability as a result of macrocyclic conjugation [15]. It is obvious that the investigation of several electronic properties, which include the delocalization of pi-electrons, benefited from studies using a range of topological approaches. In situations when it is challenging to use experimental and quantum chemical methods, graph-theoretical methods paired with topological examinations of the molecular framework have given researchers tools to examine a variety of broader PAH features [16, 17]. Analytical expressions of various degree and degree sum-based additive and multiplicative indices of larger compounds derived from hexagonal symmetric cycloarenes have been calculated in [36]. Graph entropies in terms of the fifth geometric-arithmetic index, fourth atom-bond connectivity index, and Sanskruti index-based entropies for arbitrary graphs and molecular graphs of single-walled armchair carbon nanotube Y-junctions see in [37]. On computation and analysis of topological index-based invariants for complex coronoid systems see in [38]. On characterization of physical properties for terbium (IV) oxide system via curve fitting models and structural investigation of carbon nanocone through topological coindices see in [39,40].

To characterize and assess the numerous physicochemical properties of these recently created substances, methodologies based on them require knowledge of graph theory, combinatorics, and computer-aided models. The application of precise and generalized topological quantities is required for the development of robust QSAR and QSPR models. By evaluating the structural specifics of complex compounds using the idea of molecular graphs, topological indices offer helpful approaches to detect and correlate various properties in this context. Information-theoretical

entropy, which measures how complex a molecule is, has been demonstrated to be strongly correlated with thermodynamic entropy values. As a result, it can be used to identify the phase transition between massive molecular structures. Numerous properties of molecules, including their chemical spectrum, conjugation, and aromaticity, have been quantified using the topological method and graph theory [16, 18–21]. Numerous benzoid and coronoid hydrocarbons have already been given topological characterization in the literature [6, 16, 21–24]. Due to their cyclic conjugation and D_{6h} symmetry, cyclones like kekulene and their huge oligomers have recently attracted a lot of attention. The mathematical significance of these structures is made obvious by the similarity between their symmetry and the D₆ symmetric group. Distance- and degree-based topological indices have already been calculated for straightforward cycloarenes and kekulene oligomers [6, 21, 25]. Our research is driven by the fact that this issue still exists for large 6h-symmetric cycloarene compounds with additional benzene rings and related oligomers. Choosing important degree- and degree-sum-based indices that may accurately predict the properties of 6h symmetric cycloarenes with various pore diameters and associated oligomers is the major goal of this work. Through the elimination of other indices with weaker chemical applications, computational complexity can be decreased.

Here, several big polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons with hollow sites and total hexagonal ring condensation will be thoroughly explored. In the general 6h-symmetric cycloarenes indicated by CY(p), special attention is paid to their oligomers in the current work, where p is the quantity of ring-shaped benzene on one side of the cycloarene's periphery. Kekulene oligomers alone make it impossible to study the effects of additional benzene rings added to their periphery without also losing their 6h-symmetric cycloarene structure. The current work is the result of a thorough review of the literature [16]. The sole motivation for the parameter p comes from [16] and theoretical curiosity in building massive cavity coronoids. Since cycloarenes serve as the foundation for huge structures with specific pore diameters, they are also known as super-rings. Kekulene and its tessellations' topological index values and information entropy values have already been established [6, 16, 26]. For the universal 6h, symmetric cycloarenes gave expanded relations for computing numerous topological indices as well as numerical entropy studies with graphical comparisons for their rectangular and hexagonal oligomers. The discoveries made here are now specific instances of the earlier findings. To demonstrate the significance of the theory, we gathered information on a variety of chemical properties of these compounds created utilizing experimental and quantum chemistry techniques. The

accuracy of the indices and their applicability to the nearby structures were then assessed using correlation analysis. The scientific relationship between chemistry and graph theory is furthered by our proposed stability research of various oligomers utilizing information entropy as a practical replacement for standard thermodynamic entropy. For topological characterization, three different framework types for the broader super-ring CY (p) are considered. It is possible to create the zigzag hexagonal cycloarene system by surrounding CY(p) by itself. In the center of an armchair CY(p) molecule is a hexagonal structure with a zigzag shape, and on each of its six edges, a pyramidal arrangement of hexagonal oligomer is connected between super rings. The structure then takes on a hexagonal shape as more CY(p) molecules are fused in between these pyramidal structures. The armchair hexagonal structure, or AHC (n, p), has n circular CY (p) layers. The AHC (n, p) configurations' carbon frameworks are depicted in Fig. 1.

Figure 1 AHC(n,p) cycloarene oligomer growth patterns

2. Computational methods

Throughout the work, we shall refer to the 6h symmetric polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons as simple graph G. The expression e=uv designates the edge connecting the vertices u and v. deg(u), the degree of the vertex u in the graph G, stands for the number of other carbon atoms to

which a carbon atom u is attached. We will now discuss various graph-theoretical methods employed in our research using this model. The collection of all neighbors of v is known as N(v). The summation of all the degrees of a vertex's neighboring vertices is represented by the term "S_v." The multiplication of all the degrees of the vertex's neighboring vertices is represented by the term "M_v." is multiplied to give the vertex's multiplication degree, abbreviated as M_v. The Vertex v's Van degree is defined as; $van(v) = \frac{S_v}{M_v}$ [27]. Furthermore, the vertex v's reverse Van degree is calculated as; $rvan(v) = \frac{M_v}{S_v}$. Vertex v's R degree is defined as; $r(v) = M_v + S_v$ [28]. Additionally, the vertex v's reverse R degree, computed as; $rr(v) = \frac{1}{M_v + S_v}$. Vertex v's S degree is defined as; $s(v) = |M_v - S_v|$ [29]. Furthermore, the vertex v's reverse S degree is defined as; $rs(v) = \frac{1}{|M_v - S_v| + 1}$. R, S, and Van topological indices are given in Table 1.

Table 1 R, S, Van topological indices

Name	Definition
The first Van $Van^1(G)$	$\sum_{v \in V(G)} van(v)^2$
The second Van $Van^2(G)$	$\sum_{uv \in E(G)} van(u)van(v)$
The third Van $Van^3(G)$	$\sum_{uv \in E(G)} [van(u) + van(v)]$
The first reverse Van $Van^{1r}(G)$	$\sum_{v \in V(G)} rvan(v)^2$
The second reverse Van $Van^{2r}(G)$	$\sum_{uv \in E(G)} rvan(u)rvan(v)$
The third reverse Van $Van^{3r}(G)$	$\sum_{uv \in E(G)} [rvan(u) + rvan(v)]$
The first R index $R^1(G)$	$\sum_{v \in V(G)} r(v)^2$

The second R index $R^2(G) =$	$\sum_{uv \in E(G)} r(u)r(v)$
The third R index $R^3(G) =$	$\sum_{uv \in E(G)} [r(u) + r(v)]$
The first reverse R index $R^{1r}(G)$	$\sum_{v \in V(G)} rr(v)^2$
The second reverse R $R^{2r}(G)$	$\sum_{uv \in E(G)} rr(u)rr(v)$
The third reverse R index $R^{3r}(G)$	$\sum_{uv \in E(G)} [rr(u) + rr(v)]$
The first S index $S^1(G)$	$\sum_{v \in V(G)} s(v)^2$
The second S index $S^2(G)$	$\sum_{uv \in E(G)} s(u)s(v)$
The third S index $S^2(G)$	$\sum_{uv \in E(G)} [s(u) + s(v)]$
The first reverse S index $S^{1r}(G)$	$\sum_{v \in V(G)} rs(v)^2$
The second reverse S $S^{2r}(G)$	$\sum_{uv \in E(G)} rs(u)rs(v)$
The third reverse S index $S^{3r}(G)$	$\sum_{uv \in E(G)} [rs(u) + rs(v)]$

Mathematicians can connect graph elements like edges and vertices with probability distributions using graph entropy measurements, which are divided into intrinsic and extrinsic measures. Chemistry, ecology, sociology, and biology are just a few of the disciplines that frequently use graph entropies [30, 31]. Information functional-based graph entropies were developed, evaluated, and presented by Dehmer [32, 33]. In addition to analyzing the walk-

based graph entropies, Estrada et al. [34] defined graph entropy that is valid from a physical standpoint. Applications for entropy network measurements include deriving a quantitative definition of a molecular structure and analyzing the biological and chemical characteristics of molecular graphs [35]. Entropy metrics have many applications in the analysis of chemical graphs. They are employed to look at the chemical properties of intricate networks. According to the definition of Shannon's entropy for 2D networks based on the topological index T, defined as;

$$Entropy_T(G) = Ent_T(G)$$

$$= \log(T(G)) - \frac{1}{T(G)} \sum_{uv \in E(G)} f(uv) \log(f(uv))$$

where f is the topological index's structural-functional identifier. In the case of the second Van index, for instance, $f(uv) = van(u)van(v)$ and in the case of the third Van index, for instance, $f(uv) = van(u) + van(v)$.

3. Main Results

In this section, we first determine the Van, R, and S topological indices for AHC(n, p) families, followed by the associated entropies of these indices. As shown in Fig. 2, fix a super-ring in the center, one side of which has a benzene p number, and let n be the number of dimensions of hexagonal oligomers.

Table 2 shows the sum, and multiplication edge end vertex degree, and Table 3 shows Van, S, and R edge degree divisions of AHC(n,p) families.

Table 2 Sum and multiplication degree partition of AHC(n,p).

Cardinality	(S_u, S_v)	(M_u, M_v)
$6(2n - 1)$	(5,5)	(6,6)
$12(2n - 1)$	(5,7)	(6,12)
$12(35n + 4p - 11np + 9n^2p - 27n^2 - 13)$	(6,7)	(9,12)
$12(9n^2 - 13n + 5)$	(6,8)	(9,18)
$3(9n^2 - 11n + 4)(p - 3)$	(7,7)	(12,12)

$12(2n - 1)$	(7,8)	(12,18)
$6(18n^2 - 28n + 11)$	(8,8)	(18,18)

Table 3 Novel degree partitions of AHC(n,p).

S degree	Reverse S degree	R degree	Reverse R degree	Van degree	Reverse Van degree
(1,1)	(1/2,1/2)	(11,11)	(1/11,1/11)	(5/6,5/6)	(6/5,6/5)
(1,5)	(1/2,1/6)	(11,19)	(1/11,1/19)	(5/6,7/12)	(6/5,12/7)
(3,5)	(1/4,1/6)	(15,19)	(1/15,1/19)	(2/3,7/12)	(3/2,12/7)
(3,10)	(1/4,1/11)	(15,26)	(1/15,1/26)	(2/3,4/9)	(3/2,9/4)
(5,5)	(1/6,1/6)	(19,19)	(1/19,1/19)	(7/12,7/12)	(12/7,12/7)
(5,10)	(1/6,1/11)	(19,26)	(1/19,1/26)	(7/12,4/9)	(12/7,9/4)
(10,10)	(1/11,1/11)	(26,26)	(1/26,1/26)	(4/9,4/9)	(9/4,9/4)

3.1 Topological indices AHC(n,p)

The representations of the total Van, R, and S indices for AHC(n,p) are provided by the following theorems.

Theorem 1. Let G denote an AHC(n,p) chemical graph. The second Van index of G is;

$$Van^2(G) = \frac{819}{16}n^2p - \frac{4811}{48}n^2 - \frac{1001}{16}np + \frac{62137}{432}n + \frac{91}{4}p - \frac{5963}{108}$$

Proof. Considering that G is an AHC(n,p) network. By definition;

$$Van^2(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} van(u)van(v)$$

As a result of using Table 3; the conclusion follows.

Theorem 2. Let G denote an AHC(n,p) chemical graph. The second reverse Van index of G is;

$$Van^{2r}(G) = \frac{17496}{49}n^2p - \frac{31347}{196}n^2 - \frac{21384}{49}np + \frac{187623}{1225}n + \frac{7776}{49}p - \frac{489}{9800}$$

Proof. Considering that G is an AHC(n,p) network. By definition;

$$Van^{2r}(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} rvan(u)rvan(v)$$

As a result of using Table 3; the conclusion follows.

Theorem 3. Let G denote an AHC(n,p) chemical graph. The third Van index of G is;

$$Van^3(G(m,n)) = \frac{333}{2}n^2p - \frac{567}{2}n^2 - \frac{407}{2}np + \frac{793}{2}n + 74p - 151$$

Proof. Considering that G is an AHC(n,p) network. By definition;

$$Van^3(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} (van(u) + van(v))$$

As a result of using Table 3; the conclusion follows.

Theorem 4. Let G denote an AHC(n,p) chemical graph. The third reverse Van index of G is;

$$Van^{3r}(G) = \frac{3078}{7}n^2p - \frac{2997}{7}n^2 - \frac{3762}{7}np + \frac{18981}{35}n + \frac{1368}{7}p - \frac{997}{5}$$

Proof. Considering that G is an AHC(n,p) network. By definition;

$$Van^{3r}(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} (rvan(u) + rvan(v))$$

If the values in the relevant table are written in the sum formula above, the result is obtained.

Theorem 5. Let G denote an AHC(n,p) chemical graph. The second S index of G is;

$$S^2(G) = 2295n^2p + 7155n^2 - 2805np - 11373n + 1020p + 4494$$

Proof. Considering that is an AHC(n,p) network. By definition;

$$S^2(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} s(u)s(v)$$

If the values in the relevant table are written in the sum formula above, the result is obtained.

Theorem 6. Let G denote an AHC(n,p) chemical graph. The second reverse S index of G is;

$$S^{2r}(G) = \frac{21}{4}n^2p - \frac{6363}{484}n^2 - \frac{77}{12}np + \frac{10569}{484}n + \frac{7}{3}p - \frac{96}{11}$$

Proof. Considering that is an AHC(n,p) network. By definition;

$$S^{2r}(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} rs(u)rs(v)$$

If the values in the relevant table are written in the sum formula above, the result is obtained.

Theorem 7. Let G denote an AHC(n,p) chemical graph. The third S index of G is;

$$S^3(G) = 1134n^2p + 162n^2 - 1386np - 510n + 504p + 228$$

Proof. Considering that is an AHC(n,p) network. By definition;

$$S^3(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} (s(u) + s(v))$$

If the values in the relevant table are written in the sum formula above, the result is obtained.

Theorem 8. Let G denote an AHC(n,p) chemical graph. The third reverse S index of G is;

$$S^{3r}(G) = 54n^2p - \frac{1341}{11}n^2 - 66np + \frac{2023}{11}n + 24p - \frac{788}{11}$$

Proof. Considering that is an AHC(n,p) network. By definition;

$$S^{3r}(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} (rs(u) + rs(v))$$

If the values in the relevant table are written in the sum formula above, the result is obtained.

Theorem 9. Let G denote an AHC(n,p) chemical graph. The second R index of G is;

$$R^2(G) = 40527n^2p - 67293n^2 - 49533np + 93995n + 18012p - 35782$$

Proof. Considering that is an AHC(n,p) network. By definition;

$$R^2(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} r(u)r(v)$$

If the values in the relevant table are written in the sum formula above, the result is obtained.

Theorem 10. Let G denote an AHC(n,p) chemical graph. The second reverse R index is;

$$R^{2r}(G) = \frac{819}{1805}n^2p - \frac{645273}{61090}n^2 - \frac{1001}{1805}np + \frac{57915862}{36910445}n + \frac{364}{89805713}p - \frac{147641780}{147641780}$$

Proof. Considering that is an AHC(n,p) network. By definition;

$$R^{2r}(G(m, n)) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} rr(u)rr(v)$$

If the values in the relevant table are written in the sum formula above, the result is obtained.

Theorem 11. Let G denote an AHC(n,p) chemical graph. The third R index of G is;

$$R^3(G) = 4698n^2p - 8730n^2 - 5742np + 12254n + 2088p - 4672$$

Proof. Considering that G is an AHC(n,p) network. By definition;

$$R^3(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} (r(u) + r(v))$$

If the values in the relevant table are written in the sum formula above, the result is obtained.

The 3D plot of the third R index of the AHC(n,p) network is shown in Figure 12.

Theorem 12. Let G denote an AHC(n,p) chemical graph. The third reverse R index of G is;

$$R^{3r}(G) = \frac{1494}{95}n^2p - \frac{42534}{1235}n^2 - \frac{1826}{95}np + \frac{676336}{13585}n + \frac{664}{95}p - \frac{260189}{13585}$$

Proof. Considering that is an AHC(n,p) network. By definition;

$$R^{3r}(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} (rr(u) + rr(v))$$

If the values in the relevant table are written in the sum formula above, the result is obtained.

3.1.2 Figures

3D plots of the Van, S, and R indices of the AHC(n,p) network are shown in Figures 1-13.

Figure 2 3D plot of second Van index of AHC(n,p)

Figure 6 3D plot of the second S index of AHC(n,p)

Figure 3 3D plot of second reverse Van index of AHC(n,p)

Figure 72 3D plot of the second reverse S index of AHC(n,p)

Figure 4 3D plot of the third Van index of AHC(n,p)

Figure 8 3D plot of the third S index of AHC(n,p)

Figure 5 3D plot of the third reverse Van index of AHC(n,p)

Figure 9 3D plot of the third reverse S index of AHC(n,p)

Figure 32 3D plot of the third R index of AHC(n,p)

Figure 40 3D plot of the second R index of AHC(n,p)

Figure 11 3D plot of the second reverse R index of AHC(n,p)

Figure 13 3D plot of the third reverse R index of AHC(n,p)

3.2 Entropies of AHC(n,p)

The following theorems give the overall entropies which are based on R, S, and Van topological indices representation of AHC(n,p).

Theorem 13. Let G be an AHC(n,p) network. Then, the entropy of G which is based on the second Van index of is;

$$Ent_{Van^2}(G) = \log\left(\frac{819}{16}n^2p - \frac{4811}{48}n^2 - \frac{1001}{16}np + \frac{62137}{432}n + \frac{91}{4}p - \frac{5963}{108}\right) - \frac{819}{16}n^2p - \frac{4811}{48}n^2 - \frac{1001}{16}np + \frac{62137}{432}n + \frac{91}{4}p - \frac{5963}{108} (6(2n - 1) \times \frac{25}{36} \times \log \frac{25}{36} + 12(2n - 1) \times \frac{35}{72} \times \log \frac{35}{72} + 12(35n + 4p - 11np + 9n^2p - 27n^2 - 13) \times \frac{7}{18} \times \log \frac{7}{18} + 12(9n^2 - 13n + 5) \times \frac{8}{27} \times \log \frac{8}{27} + 3(9n^2 - 11n + 4)(p - 3) \times \frac{49}{144} \times \log \frac{49}{144} + 12(2n - 1) \times \frac{7}{27} \times \log \frac{7}{27} + 6(18n^2 - 28n + 11) \times \frac{16}{81} \times \log \frac{16}{81})$$

Proof. Considering that G is an AHC(n,p) network. By definition;

$$Ent_{Van^2}(G) = \log(Van^2(G)) - \frac{1}{Van^2(G)} \sum_{uv \in E(G)} f(uv) \log(f(uv))$$

As a result of using Theorem 1, the conclusion follows.

Theorem 14. Let G be an AHC(n,p) network. Then, the entropy of G which is based on the second reverse Van index of is;

$$Ent_{Van^{2r}}(G) = \log\left(\frac{17496}{49}n^2p - \frac{31347}{196}n^2 - \frac{21384}{49}np + \frac{187623}{1225}n + \frac{7776}{49}p - \frac{489}{9800}\right) - \frac{17496}{49}n^2p - \frac{31347}{196}n^2 - \frac{21384}{49}np + \frac{187623}{1225}n + \frac{7776}{49}p - \frac{489}{9800} (6(2n - 1) \times \frac{36}{25} \times \log \frac{36}{25} + 12(2n - 1) \times \frac{72}{35} \times \log \frac{72}{35} + 12(35n + 4p - 11np + 9n^2p - 27n^2 - 13) \times \frac{18}{7} \times \log \frac{18}{7} + 12(9n^2 - 13n + 5) \times \frac{27}{8} \times \log \frac{27}{8} + 3(9n^2 - 11n + 4)(p - 3) \times \frac{144}{49} \times \log \frac{144}{49} + 12(2n - 1) \times \frac{27}{7} \times \log \frac{27}{7} + 6(18n^2 - 28n + 11) \times \frac{81}{16} \times \log \frac{81}{16})$$

Proof. Considering that G is an AHC(n,p) network. By definition;

$$Ent_{Van^{2r}}(G) = \log(Van^{2r}(G)) - \frac{1}{Van^{2r}(G)} \sum_{uv \in E(G)} f(uv) \log(f(uv))$$

As a result of using Theorem 2, the conclusion follows.

Theorem 15. Let G be an AHC(n,p) network. Then, the entropy of G which is based on the third Van index of is;

$$Ent_{Van^3}(G) = \log\left(\frac{333}{2}n^2p - \frac{567}{2}n^2 - \frac{407}{2}np + \frac{793}{2}n + 74p - 151\right) - \frac{1}{\frac{333}{2}n^2p - \frac{567}{2}n^2 - \frac{407}{2}np + \frac{793}{2}n + 74p - 151} (6(2n-1) \times \frac{5}{3} \times \log \frac{5}{3} + 12(2n-1) \times \frac{17}{12} \times \log \frac{17}{12} + 12(35n+4p-11np+9n^2p-27n^2-13) \times \frac{5}{4} \times \log \frac{5}{4} + 12(9n^2-13n+5) \times \frac{10}{9} \times \log \frac{10}{9} + 3(9n^2-11n+4)(p-3) \times \frac{7}{6} \times \log \frac{7}{6} + 12(2n-1) \times \frac{37}{36} \times \log \frac{37}{36} + 6(18n^2-28n+11) \times \frac{8}{9} \times \log \frac{8}{9})$$

Proof. Considering that G is an AHC(n,p) network. By definition;

$$Ent_{Van^3}(G) = \log(Van^3(G)) - \frac{1}{Van^3(G)} \sum_{uv \in E(G)} f(uv) \log(f(uv))$$

As a result of using Theorem 3, the conclusion follows.

Theorem 16. Let G be an AHC(n,p) network. Then, the entropy of G which is based on the third reverse Van index of is;

$$Ent_{Van^{3r}}(G) = \log\left(\frac{3078}{7}n^2p - \frac{2997}{7}n^2 - \frac{3762}{7}np + \frac{18981}{35}n + \frac{1368}{7}p - \frac{997}{5}\right) - \frac{1}{\frac{3078}{7}n^2p - \frac{2997}{7}n^2 - \frac{3762}{7}np + \frac{18981}{35}n + \frac{1368}{7}p - \frac{997}{5}} (6(2n-1) \times \frac{12}{5} \times \log \frac{12}{5} + 12(2n-1) \times \frac{102}{35} \times \log \frac{102}{35} + 12(35n+4p-11np+9n^2p-27n^2-13) \times \frac{15}{14} \times \log \frac{15}{14} + 12(9n^2-13n+5) \times \frac{15}{4} \times \log \frac{15}{4} + 3(9n^2-11n+4)(p-3) \times \frac{24}{7} \times \log \frac{24}{7} + 12(2n-1) \times \frac{111}{28} \times \log \frac{111}{28} + 6(18n^2-28n+11) \times \frac{9}{2} \times \log \frac{9}{2})$$

Proof. Considering that G is an AHC(n,p) network. By definition;

$$Ent_{Van^{3r}}(G) = \log(Van^{3r}(G)) - \frac{1}{Van^{3r}(G)} \sum_{uv \in E(G)} f(uv) \log(f(uv))$$

As a result of using Theorem 4, the conclusion follows.

Theorem 17. Let G be an AHC(n,p) network. Then, the entropy of G which is based on the second S index of is;

$$Ent_{S^2}(G) = \log(2295n^2p + 7155n^2 - 2805np - 11373n + 1020p + 4494) - \frac{1}{2295n^2p + 7155n^2 - 2805np - 11373n + 1020p + 4494} (12(2n-1) \times 5 \times \log 5 + 12(35n+4p-11np+9n^2p-27n^2-13) \times 15 \times \log 15 + 12(9n^2-13n+5) \times 30 \times \log 30 + 3(9n^2-11n+4)(p-3) \times 25 \times \log 5 + 12(2n-1) \times 50 \times \log 50 + 6(18n^2-28n+11) \times 100 \times \log 100)$$

Proof. Considering that G is an AHC(n,p) network. By definition;

$$Ent_{S^2}(G) = \log(S^2(G)) - \frac{1}{S^2(G)} \sum_{uv \in E(G)} f(uv) \log(f(uv))$$

As a result of using Theorem 5, the conclusion follows.

Theorem 18. Let G be an AHC(n,p) network. Then, the entropy of G which is based on the second reverse S index of is;

$$Ent_{S^{2r}}(G) = \log\left(\frac{21}{4}n^2p - \frac{6363}{484}n^2 - \frac{77}{12}np + \frac{10569}{484}n + \frac{7}{3}p - \frac{96}{11}\right) - \frac{1}{\frac{21}{4}n^2p - \frac{6363}{484}n^2 - \frac{77}{12}np + \frac{10569}{484}n + \frac{7}{3}p - \frac{96}{11}} (6(2n-1) \times \frac{1}{4} \times \log \frac{1}{4} + 12(2n-1) \times \frac{1}{12} \times \log \frac{1}{12} + 12(35n+4p-11np+9n^2p-27n^2-13) \times \frac{1}{24} \times \log \frac{1}{24} + 12(9n^2-13n+5) \times \frac{1}{44} \times \log \frac{1}{44} + 3(9n^2-11n+4)(p-3) \times \frac{1}{36} \times \log \frac{1}{36} + 12(2n-1) \times \frac{1}{66} \times \log \frac{1}{66} + 6(18n^2-28n+11) \times \frac{1}{121} \times \log \frac{1}{121})$$

Proof. Considering that G is an AHC(n,p) network. By definition;

$$Ent_{S^{2r}}(G) = \log(S^{2r}(G)) - \frac{1}{S^{2r}(G)} \sum_{uv \in E(G)} f(uv) \log(f(uv))$$

As a result of using Theorem 6, the conclusion follows.

Theorem 19. Let G be an AHC(n,p) network. Then, the entropy of G which is based on the third S index of is;

$$Ent_{S^3}(G) = \log(1134n^2p + 162n^2 - 1386np - 510n + 504p + 228) - \frac{1}{1134n^2p + 162n^2 - 1386np - 510n + 504p + 228} (6(2n-1) \times 2 \times \log 2 + 12(2n-1) \times 6 \times \log 6 + 12(35n+4p-11np+9n^2p-27n^2-13) \times 8 \times \log 8 + 12(9n^2-13n+5) \times 13 \times \log 13 + 3(9n^2-11n+4)(p-3) \times 10 \times \log 10 + 12(2n-1) \times 15 \times \log 15 + 6(18n^2-28n+11) \times 20 \times \log 20)$$

Proof. Considering that G is an AHC(n,p) network. By definition;

$$Ent_{S^3}(G) = \log(S^3(G)) - \frac{1}{S^3(G)} \sum_{uv \in E(G)} f(uv) \log(f(uv))$$

As a result of using Theorem 7, the conclusion follows.

Theorem 20. Let G be an AHC(n,p) network. Then, the entropy of G which is based on the third reverse S index of is;

$$Ent_{S^{3r}}(G) = \log\left(54n^2p - \frac{1341}{11}n^2 - 66np + \frac{2023}{11}n + 24p - \frac{788}{11}\right) - \frac{1}{54n^2p - \frac{1341}{11}n^2 - 66np + \frac{2023}{11}n + 24p - \frac{788}{11}} (12(2n-1) \times \frac{2}{3} \times \log \frac{2}{3} + 12(35n+4p-11np+9n^2p-27n^2-13) \times \frac{5}{12} \times \log \frac{5}{12} + 12(9n^2-13n+5) \times \frac{15}{44} \times \log \frac{15}{44} + 3(9n^2-11n+4)(p-3) \times \frac{1}{3} \times \log \frac{1}{3} + 12(2n-1) \times \frac{17}{66} \times \log \frac{17}{66} + 6(18n^2-28n+11) \times \frac{2}{11} \times \log \frac{2}{11})$$

Proof. Considering that G is an AHC(n,p) network. By definition;

$$Ent_{S^{3r}}(G) = \log(S^{3r}(G)) - \frac{1}{S^{3r}(G)} \sum_{uv \in E(G)} f(uv) \log(f(uv))$$

As a result of using Theorem 8, the conclusion follows.

Theorem 21. Let G be an AHC(n,p) network. Then, the entropy of G which is based on the second R index of is;

$$Ent_{R^2}(G) = \log(40527n^2p - 67293n^2 - 49533np + 93995n + 18012p - 35782) - \frac{1}{40527n^2p - 67293n^2 - 49533np + 93995n + 18012p - 35782} (6(2n-1) \times 121 \times \log 121)$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \log 121 + 12(2n - 1) \times 209 \times \log 209 + 12(35n + 4p - 11np + \\ & 9n^2p - 27n^2 - 13) \times 285 \times \log 285 \\ & + 12(9n^2 - 13n + 5) \times 390 \times \log 390 + 3(9n^2 - 11n + 4)(p \\ & - 3) \times 361 \times \log 361 + 12(2n \\ & - 1) \times 494 \times \log 494 \\ & + 6(18n^2 - 28n + 11) \times 676 \times \log 676 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Considering that G is an AHC(n,p) network. By definition;

$$\begin{aligned} Ent_{R^2}(G) &= \log(R^2(G)) \\ & - \frac{1}{R^2(G)} \sum_{uv \in E(G)} f(uv) \log(f(uv)) \end{aligned}$$

As a result of using Theorem 9, the conclusion follows.

Theorem 22. Let G be an AHC(n,p) network. Then, the entropy of G which is based on the second reverse R index of is;

$$\begin{aligned} Ent_{R^{2r}}(G) &= \log \left(\frac{819}{1805} n^2 p - \frac{645273}{610090} n^2 - \frac{1001}{1805} np + \frac{57915862}{36910445} n + \right. \\ & \left. \frac{364}{1805} p - \frac{89805713}{147641780} \right) - \\ & \frac{1}{\frac{819}{1805} n^2 p - \frac{645273}{610090} n^2 - \frac{1001}{1805} np + \frac{57915862}{36910445} n + \frac{364}{1805} p - \frac{89805713}{147641780}} (6(2n - 1) \times \frac{1}{121} \times \\ & \log \frac{1}{121} + 12(2n - 1) \times \frac{1}{209} \times \log \frac{1}{209} + 12(35n + 4p - 11np + \\ & 9n^2p - 27n^2 - 13) \times \frac{1}{285} \times \log \frac{1}{285} + 12(9n^2 - 13n + 5) \times \frac{1}{390} \times \\ & \log \frac{1}{390} + 3(9n^2 - 11n + 4)(p - 3) \times \frac{1}{361} \times \log \frac{1}{361} + 12(2n - 1) \times \\ & \frac{1}{494} \times \log \frac{1}{494} + 6(18n^2 - 28n + 11) \times \frac{1}{676} \times \log \frac{1}{676}) \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Considering that G is an AHC(n,p) network. By definition;

$$\begin{aligned} Ent_{R^{2r}}(G) &= \log(R^{2r}(G)) - \frac{1}{R^{2r}(G)} \sum_{uv \in E(G)} f(uv) \log(f(uv)) \end{aligned}$$

As a result of using Theorem 10, the conclusion follows.

Theorem 23. Let G be an AHC(n,p) network. Then, the entropy of G which is based on the third R index of is;

$$\begin{aligned} Ent_{R^3}(G) &= \log(4698n^2p - 8730n^2 - 5742np + 12254n + \\ & 2088p - 4672) - \frac{1}{4698n^2p - 8730n^2 - 5742np + 12254n + 2088p - 4672} (6(2n - \\ & 1) \times 22 \times \log 22 + 12(2n - 1) \times 30 \times \log 30 + 12(35n + 4p - \\ & 11np + 9n^2p - 27n^2 - 13) \times 34 \times \log 34 + 12(9n^2 - 13n + 5) \times \\ & 41 \times \log 41 + 3(9n^2 - 11n + 4)(p - 3) \times 38 \times \log 38 + 12(2n - \\ & 1) \times 45 \times \log 45 + 6(18n^2 - 28n + 11) \times 52 \times \log 52) \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Considering that G is an AHC(n,p) network. By definition;

$$\begin{aligned} Ent_{R^3}(G) &= \log(R^3(G)) \\ & - \frac{1}{R^3(G)} \sum_{uv \in E(G)} f(uv) \log(f(uv)) \end{aligned}$$

As a result of using Theorem 11, the conclusion follows.

Theorem 24. Let G be an AHC(n,p) network. Then, the entropy of G which is based on the third reverse R index of is;

$$\begin{aligned} Ent_{R^{3r}}(G) &= \log \left(\frac{1494}{95} n^2 p - \frac{42534}{1235} n^2 - \frac{1826}{95} np + \frac{676336}{13585} n + \right. \\ & \left. \frac{664}{95} p - \frac{260189}{13585} \right) - \frac{1}{\frac{1494}{95} n^2 p - \frac{42534}{1235} n^2 - \frac{1826}{95} np + \frac{676336}{13585} n + \frac{664}{95} p - \frac{260189}{13585}} (6(2n - 1) \times \\ & \frac{2}{11} \times \log \frac{2}{11} + 12(2n - 1) \times \frac{30}{209} \times \log \frac{30}{209} + 12(35n + 4p - 11np + \\ & 9n^2p - 27n^2 - 13) \times \frac{34}{285} \times \log \frac{34}{285} + 12(9n^2 - 13n + 5) \times \frac{41}{390} \times \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \log \frac{41}{390} + 3(9n^2 - 11n + 4)(p - 3) \times \frac{2}{19} \times \log \frac{2}{19} + 12(2n - 1) \times \\ & \frac{45}{494} \times \log \frac{45}{494} + 6(18n^2 - 28n + 11) \times \frac{1}{13} \times \log \frac{1}{13}) \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Considering that G is an AHC(n,p) network. By definition;

$$\begin{aligned} Ent_{R^3r}(G) &= \log(R^{3r}(G)) - \frac{1}{R^{3r}(G)} \sum_{uv \in E(G)} f(uv) \log(f(uv)) \end{aligned}$$

As a result of using Theorem 12, the conclusion follows.

4. Conclusions

This work describes the generalized mathematical equation for R, S, and Van topological indices for structures of AHC(n,p). These generalized mathematical formulations give information-theoretic entropy measurements of several phases of 2D materials of AHC(n,p). It was discovered that the structures we looked at here have very little variety in their entropies. Using our suggested topological indices and entropy metrics, we may anticipate the thermochemistry, physicochemical properties, electrical, optical, and mechanical features of these numerous AHC(n,p) phases. These indices can also be paired with metrics from quantum chemistry, such as molecular hardness, polarizability measurements, atomic charges, etc., to build a platform that is effective for forecasting molecular connections and electronic-based properties. The same method is used to generate a large number of probabilistic entropy measurements.

Conflict of Interest

The author declares that having no competing interests

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